

Cultural Diplomacy and Cultural Tourism Development: The Case with Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Cultural diplomacy is strategic for marketing national identities and attracting international tourism inflows for economic development. Its functionality and efficiency in driving a tourism-based development in regions like Nigeria is, however, significantly marred by narrow perceptions, lack of in-depth exploration and inadequate implementation frameworks. This study, postulating a correlation between cultural diplomacy and cultural tourism development, examines Nigeria's cultural diplomacy against the backdrop of its vast cultural resources to identifying its strengths and weaknesses in attracting culturally motivated international tourists and investors for cultural tourism-based and sustainable development. It examines relevant literature, policy documents, Nigeria's cultural resources and current efforts by state and non-state actors, to identify the gaps and inadequacies that must be addressed to harness the benefits of cultural diplomacy and channel them towards securing tangible economic benefits. Recommendations are made, based on the identified gaps and inadequacies. The study provides useful leads for policy action, government inter-ministerial synergy, stakeholder collaborations, and local community involvement in tourism development.

Keywords: *Cultural diplomacy, cultural tourism, tourism-based development, sustainability, national identity, destination image branding.*

1. Introduction

The post-pandemic phase of the 21st Century has witnessed an increased prominence of cultural tourism in the global indices for market growth and economic development. This is in spite of the exponential surge in global geopolitical and economic discomforts and their adverse effects on tourism activities. A significant 40% of global tourism revenue derives from cultural tourism alone (UNWTO, 2023). Similarly, the Allied Market Research for 2022 placed the market value of global heritage tourism at USD 639 billion with a growth forecast of over 1 trillion by the year 2032. Additionally, the World Economic Forum (2025) projects a \$16 trillion contribution by the travel and tourism sector to the global GDP by the year 2034 up from the current \$7 trillion, most of which is expected to be generated by cultural and heritage related travel and tourism. Consequently, both state and non-state actors across national divides have adopted multiple strategies and approaches in marketing their cultural identities and products, seeking wider consumption bases across borders for the promotion of cultural tourism in their various domains. Cultural diplomacy is an inimitable component of these strategies. Using their various cultural capital that include food, drink, arts, theatre, education, technology, sights and sounds, and other social engagements, states and non-state actors have sought to create and maintain diplomatic relations and secure positions of relative cultural advantage for themselves in the comity of nations.

On the other hand, the rather narrow perception of cultural diplomacy as a mere component of public diplomacy, and the dearth of its in-depth exploration and application by governments and researchers in most African nations, including Nigeria, have robbed it of its functionality and efficiency in improving these nations and attracting international tourism inflows and integral economic development. Besides, Nigeria, as the most culturally diverse country in the West African sub-region, not only traverses the Sudanic Savannah and the Guinea Coast geo-cultural divides; it also has had various waves of migration and cross-cultural contacts across its territories over time through trade, religion and political processes that have given

it a unique blend of the cultures of the Niger-Congo, Nilo-Saharan and the Afro-Asiatic groups of languages. However, its cultural tourism development index has remained significantly low and unimpressive over time, while its framework for cultural diplomacy implementation seems invisible, non-deliberate, and unable to yield tangible results. For instance, the World Economic Forum's Travel and Tourism Development index for 2024 gives Nigeria a score of 3.18, lower than Egypt (3.96) and South Africa (3.99). This also assigns Nigeria the 112th position in the global ranking, lower than many other African countries in sub-Saharan Africa (World Economic Forum, 2024). This is unacceptable, especially given Nigeria's strategic identity in the region and its immense human and economic endowments.

This discourse, which postulates a correlation between cultural diplomacy and cultural tourism development, explores this correlation in the case of Nigeria. It interrogates the current state of Nigeria's cultural diplomatic schemes and how they could generate cultural interest in their place of origin, especially given Nigeria's vast cultural capital. Through a critical and hermeneutical review of relevant literature and policy documents, with an appraisal of current practices, it examines how cultural diplomacy could better stimulate cultural tourism development in Nigeria by attracting culturally motivated international visitors and increased diaspora engagement. Recommendations are made, based on identified gaps and weaknesses, for repositioning cultural diplomacy as a sustainable driver of cultural tourism development, economic diversification and global influence.

2. An Overview of Cultural Diplomacy

Cultural diplomacy has evolved from the level of official interchange between the courts of rulers to being a multifaceted soft power used by modern nation states to project their national identities to the international public. However, there seems to be a rather weak discrimination by researchers between the conceptual integrity of *cultural diplomacy*, its scope and purposes on the one hand, and the manners in which nations have actually used it in contemporary times. A contemporary and unsophisticated description of cultural diplomacy frames it as: "a course of actions, which are based on and utilize the exchange of ideas, values, traditions and other aspects of culture or identity, whether to strengthen relationships, enhance

sociocultural cooperation or promote national interests; ... can be practiced by either the public sector, private sector or civil society” (Constantinescu, quoted in Cultural Diplomacy, 2013: 30). It is also a ‘means through which countries promote their cultural and political values to the rest of the world, ... to allow people access to different cultures and perspectives, and in this way, foster mutual understanding and dialogue’. As such, it ‘is practiced by a range of actors including national governments, public and private sector institutions, and civil societies’ (Cultural Diplomacy, 2013: 30). From a global perspective, cultural diplomacy has been broadly understood to include efforts made by non-state actors, including organisations, individuals and scholars in the fields of cultural studies, anthropology, sociology and international relations that seek to project and celebrate global cultural diversity and promote mutual respect among global cultures. However, given that diplomacy itself is, technically speaking, a state function, the active participation of non-state actors in cultural diplomacy seem to obscure its diplomatic status, or at least compel a distinction between cultural relations and cultural diplomacy (Mitchell, 1986; Mark, 2009).

Some studies have seen cultural diplomacy as precursory to, rather than as a subfield of public diplomacy and distinct from the cultural dimensions of international relations (Savaş, 2024), while others view it as occupying the interface between public diplomacy and cultural relations (Kim, 2017). Still others have seen it as a distinct sub-set of public diplomacy, but requiring further conceptual pruning to distinguish it from public diplomacy and other related concepts (Zervaki, 2025; Goff, 2013; Mark, 2009; Knight, 2022). It can, therefore, be said that while public diplomacy encompasses the wider communicative measures adopted by nations to tell the world who they are, cultural diplomacy involves their uses of culture to demonstrate to the world what they have to share. Nevertheless, it can also be reasonably argued that the apparent lack of precision on the meaning of the concept stems not from its nature and practice, but from the seemingly boundlessness of what constitutes the *cultural* in cultural diplomacy. In the attempt to navigate this fragile terrain, some scholars (Bettie, 2019; Grincheva, 2010; Chaubet, 2004) have proposed what seems like an undue fragmentation of culture along the lines of exchange, arts and language. Yet, it is logical to argue that the conceptual identity of cultural

diplomacy rests in its engagement of cultural means – ideational, popular, tangible and intangible – and all that these imply in the conduct of diplomacy. In other words, it is ‘the deployment of a state’s culture in support of its foreign policy goals or diplomacy’ (Mark, 2009:1). The implication here, is that where a state fails to clearly define its cultural capital, it might be impossible to deploy such for any diplomatic objectives.

It has also been suggested that cultural diplomacy necessarily happens abroad (Mark, 2009). In this case, the government of New Zealand, for instance, sees it as ‘the international presentation of cultural activities by a state to improve understanding of its cultural life and to create a favourable image in order to facilitate improved diplomatic and trade relationship’ (Ministry of Culture and Heritage, NZ, 2000; Mark, 2009). This also often includes a state’s propagating of its language, policy and point of view abroad (Cummings, 2003). Mark (2009: 7-11) identifies some ‘core elements of cultural diplomacy’ that streamline its operational identity. These include its *objectives*, which have governments and their agencies as the essential actors, and consist in fostering international mutual understanding and fighting discrimination, while the practical *intentions* comprise improving economic, political, diplomatic and other ties, including bilateral support during conflicts. Other elements are: the main *activities*, which include language, academic exchange programmes and cultural activities from the creative industries; and *audience*, which includes nations abroad and persons in the diaspora.

The functional potency of cultural diplomacy derives from the internal collaboration and coordinated strategies among stakeholders, with increased funding to serve as a vibrant force that guarantees the interaction rather than the clashing of civilisations, and in this way enable it attain its full potentials (Schneider, 2009). Meanwhile, owing to its low perception by diplomatic and political actors and the challenge in getting accurate forecast of its impact on the public – with the subtle but real distinction between its praxis and international cultural relations – scholarly engagement on the subject remains sparse (Mark, 2009). A distinction is also made between the cold-war-era type of cultural diplomacy as popularised by the super power actors in their pursuit of socio-political rivalry, and others, such as are used by nations of the so called *Third World* and the *Global South* for creating inter-state

harmony, often with economic undertones (Clarke, 2020). Despite such distinctions, the full sway of cultural diplomacy on tourism development remains grossly underexplored.

3. Cultural Diplomacy and Tourism Development

Although the relationship between tourism, diplomacy, politics, and integral development has been the subject of various studies (Negassa, 2024; Bowen et al, 2017; Demir & Demir, 2025; Nwala & Gesiere, 2024), specific and contextualised insights on cultural diplomacy's contributions to cultural tourism development is sparse. However, some studies have adjudged cultural diplomacy as efficient in tourism development, especially in the image making and identity formation of tourism destinations (Papageorgiou & Papagianni, 2018), owing to the decisive sway wielded by culture on tourists of various genres. Others opine that the functionality of the relationship between cultural diplomacy and tourism development, especially at the international level, largely depend on the effective application of cultural heritage administration strategies that draw from communal involvement (Carbone, 2017). Similarly, Clarke (2016) opines that a more integral understanding of the imports of cultural diplomacy could be attained through a critical evaluation of the role of cultural products and how such products are received by other nations. Even when considered from the perspective of foreign aids programmes, as in the case of Japan (Akagawa (2014), there is an interconnectedness between cultural diplomacy, heritage conservation policy and practice, and national identity as foreign aids programmes are measures of both cultural diplomacy and heritage conservation that have served to preserve national identities as well as enhance their regional and global positive image.

At a pragmatic level, cultural diplomacy has proven immensely successful in advancing not only tourism development but a wide range of other wealth creating and image building ventures across continental divides. For instance, a deliberate tourism promotion programme by the Indonesian Ministry of Tourism in Saudi Arabia between 2015 and 2018, using a blend of some UNESCO recognised world's intangible cultural heritage programmes and a touch of Islamic culture was adjudged as largely successful (Putri *et al.*, 2021). Unfortunately, some countries seem unable

to create and maintain a synergy between their cultural wealth, the creative industries and their diplomatic endeavours in a manner that yields sustainable development (Lara-Ortiz, 2022; Pudaruth, 2017).

In Nigeria, studies that highlight the pivotal role of government measures and non-state actors, especially persons in the creative industries, in driving contemporary tourism development are current. In a study of the Nigerian entertainment industry's role in national development through cultural diplomacy, Sotubo and Chidozie (2014), appraise musicians, actors and other entertainers as virtual ambassadors that market Nigeria's cultural contents and values to the global society, and in turn attract income and investment into the country. Similarly, Nwala and Gesiere (2024) explore the interface between tourism development and soft power diplomacy, especially in the Niger Delta Region, with emphasis on such deliberate actions like cultural exchange, local community involvement, environmental consciousness, and others, for integral development. However, while resources and opportunities seem to abound for the use of its cultural capital for integral development, Nigeria requires a more deliberate and official commitment to a cultural diplomacy that aims at harvesting greater tourism inflows into its territories. In this respect, David and Ugwu (2024) suggest that Nigeria could use its rich and diverse cultural capital not only to foster its diplomatic ties with nations like the US, but also to streamline its foreign policies and promote global peace.

Some studies have pointed to certain drawbacks such as weaknesses in policies and in implementation mechanisms. Afolabi *et al* (2022) critique the 1988 Nigerian Cultural Policy's lack of affirmation of the Nigerian Film industry (the Nollywood) in its corpus, especially given Nollywood's representativeness, its strategic role in promoting Nigeria's identity and the document's role in guiding such promotional endeavours. In the same vein, although Nollywood has been outstanding in projecting Nigeria's cultural identity, securing jobs and creating wealth, certain forces obscure its optimal performance, such as intellectual property theft, infrastructural deficit and unsophisticated content (Adoke & Saidu, 2022). Additionally, Ododo (2022) identifies Nigeria's National Theatre and the National Troup as formidable forces in harmonising Nigeria's cultural diversity for greater understanding within and outside the country, but which require more vibrant

operational charter. Other resources, like the Swange music and dance of the Tivi people of the Benue have been identified as major drivers of contemporary cultural diplomacy in Nigeria (Justin, 2019) that could consistently attract tangible developmental benefits to the tourism sector.

4. Nigeria's Cultural Capital for Enhanced Cultural Diplomacy

Nigeria's unique geographical and historical ambiances, as mentioned above, have been shaped by multiple streams of migration and cross-cultural encounters. These have combined to bestow it with a rich blend of diverse cultural resources that are critical to building strategic cultural diplomacy and enduring cultural tourism development. The nation's cultural capital includes various tangible and intangible assets that comprise the performing arts; oral traditions and expressions; social practices, rituals and festive events; knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe; and traditional craftsmanship. These in addition to its historic and archaeological sites, diverse cuisine and general gastronomic culture. Its arts and the creative industry comprising film and television; theatre and stage performances; music industry; standup comedy and skits; dance and choreography; circus and puppetry; the spoken word and poetry constitute a robust cultural pipeline that can enrich cultural diplomacy and tourism development in multiple ways.

Nollywood, Nigeria's film and television industry is rated as the second largest in the world by volume, with a global audience spanning across Africa, the Caribbean, North America and the rest of the world. It serves as a major cultural export that draws domestic and international tourists to shooting locations and film festivals (Nwosu & Uche, 2019). With the weapons of popular culture, informality and global outreach, Nollywood amplifies themes that resonate with some contemporary Nigerian and African experiences, such as urbanity and migration, cultural identity affirmation, spirituality and traditional cosmologies, moral and social anxieties, survival strategies and others. Similarly, the music industry that gained popularity and gathered significant momentum through highlife, juju and afro music from the days of Fela Ransome Kuti (1938-1997), Sir Victor Uwaifo (1941-2021), King Sunny Ade and others, has become a global phenomenon in contemporary Afrobeats with such iconic artists as Davido, Rema, Burna Boy, Wizkid, Tems, Ayra Starr and

others, projecting the Nigerian identity and lifestyle to the global community. Nigeria's creativity capital is equally visible in the realms of literature in which such global iconic personalities like Chinua Achebe, Wole Soyinka and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie have shaped global discourses on postcolonial narratives, social identity and cultural authenticity, among others. Additionally, Nigeria is well endowed with various other creative resources by way of oral traditions and linguistic expressions, performing arts, circus and puppetry spread across the various ethnic nationalities within its geo-political boundaries that are recognised and celebrated by the United Nations and constitute veritable soft power and vital weapons for contemporary cultural diplomacy and tourism development.

There are numerous festivals, knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe, rituals, social practices and traditional craftsmanship that also form part of Nigeria's cultural capital. These include the Kwagh-Hir performance of the Benue region, the Calabar Carnival, the Ekpe masquerade ritual among the Efik, the *Ofala* festival of Onitsha, the ritual breaking and eating of the Kola Nut among the Igbo, the New Yam festival, The Eyo, Ijele, Zangbeto, Igunnuko, Oro, the Gelede masquerade and its oral heritage, the *Inmole* festival that celebrates the Earth Spirits, the Sango festival, the Ifa divination system, the Osun Oshogbo festival and the *Talking Drum* among the Yoruba, The Argungu fishing festival of Kebbi State, the Durba Festival, and numerous crafts and knowledge systems across the various regions and the tangible cultural products associated with them. These events and practices not only provide rich platforms for cultural diplomatic exchange and international tourism inflows, but also create channels for the exchange of cultural commodities that could boost traditional industries, create economic benefits and make way for tourism-led development.

Other resources include national monuments and heritage sites, vibrant culinary culture and fashion. Among the cultural heritage sites are the Sukur Cultural Landscape in Madagali, Adamawa State, the Benin City Walls and Moat in Benin, Edo State, the Osun-Oshogbo Sacred Grove in Oshogbo, Osun State, the Ancient Kano City Walls and Gates, the Nok Culture Sites in Kano State, the various Rock paintings in Jigawa State, Ancient Palaces in southern and northern Nigeria, pre-

colonial and colonial heritage sites especially in the eastern, southern and western States of Nigeria, and the various Museums that house the relics of the nation's early civilization, material culture and crafts. The culinary culture of Nigeria, deriving from the geo-ecological variation of its landscape and the cultural diversity of the various ethnic nationalities, has a unique blend of grains, tubers, fruits, seeds, vegetables, crops, spices, animal-based products, extracts and beverages that are found across its various regions (Embassy of the Federal Republic of Nigeria to the Netherlands, 2023). While some of these have gained global popularity and recognition over the years, especially through Nigerians in the diaspora, others are celebrated nationally while others still are local delicacies in their specific regions of domicile. The abundant recipes from leafy vegetables used for different sauces and spicy soups perfectly complement the root, tuber, grain and seed based foods and puddings like *garri*, *iyam*, *akpu*, *akara*, *moin-moin*, *jollof*, *ofada*, plantain, *tuwo*, *masa*, *dan wake*, and many others that are highly celebrated across the nation. There are spicy kebabs, grills and barbecue from fish, beef, mutton, pork and poultry, like *suya*, *balangu*, *kilishi*, *nkwobi*, and many others all of which offer unique gastronomic experiences. There are also various natural unprocessed and processed drinks and beverages like palm wine, coconut drinks, *ogogoro*, *kunun zaki*, *fura da nono* and others, as well as snacks, pastries, and crunchy cookies that make up the Nigerian culinary heritage. Additionally, there are a number of Nigerian celebrity chefs that are gaining significant international recognition through prestigious awards and widespread media exposure like Adejoke Bakare, the first black female Michelin-starred chef in the United Kingdom, while others are building global profiles through media activity, world records and influential culinary outlets abroad, like Hilda Effiong Basse (Hilda Baci). Also, the Nigerian fashion industry specially driven by such local fabrics and styles like the *Ankara*, *aso oke*, *baban riga*, and others, is widely celebrated. These provide ample opportunities and vibrant resources for cultural diplomacy and tourism boost.

5. Current Government and Institutional Efforts

Current efforts at strategically repositioning Nigeria's cultural diplomacy for integral cultural tourism development seem weak and non-resilient. There is the absence of a

well-defined policy framework for cultural diplomacy implementation by state and non-state actors. However, a significant milestone in this direction, from the tourism perspective, is the ongoing initiative by the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Art, Culture, Tourism, and Creative Economy with the support of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) and the National Economic Summit Group (NESG) to revise and update the national cultural policy of 1988 to reflect current realities, align with global best practices and optimize tourism development. Among the core objectives of this initiative are the global projection of Nigeria's cultural capital and the entrenchment of a cultural governance system that is operational and visible (Ajaegbo, 2025), which perfectly align with cultural diplomacy practices. However, it is important to note that this is not the first attempt by the federal government at bridging the policy gap between its cultural capital and integral tourism development. A robust attempt in this direction was made in 2025 with the fabrication of a *Nigerian Tourism Development Master Plan (2025)*, which, in the words of the then Secretary General of the World Tourism Organisation, aimed at promoting 'the sustainable development of the tourism industry through capacity building of the Government (at the Federal level) in the areas of human resource development, research development, improved sectorial planning and governance' as well as encouraging effective local community participation in the process (Frangialli, 2025: f). This project jointly funded by the Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, the United Nations World Tourism Organisation, the United Nations Development Programme, and executed by Tourism Development International, a private firm, contained several poignant observations with strategic recommendations. There is also a *National Hospitality and Tourism Policy* that was reviewed in 2024, and the *Nigerian Tourism Development Authority Act (2022)* that repealed the former Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation Act, all meant to regulate the Nigerian tourism industry and give it a sense of direction through specific directives and mandates. Although these policy initiatives do not directly address the intersection between cultural diplomacy and tourism development, they nevertheless, provide a framework for addressing the dearth in government inter-ministerial and inter-agency synergy, especially the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the

Nigerian Tourism Development Authority (NTDA) and the Ministry of Art, Tourism, Culture, and Creative Economy in charting an upward trajectory in this direction.

There are localised and isolated efforts by some federal ministries, agencies and state governments and other institutions at consolidating Nigeria's cultural capital, enhancing its global visibility and creating incentives for cultural diplomacy and tourism development. For instance, the Female Artists Association of Nigeria (FEAAN) established in 2001 represented Nigeria at the 2025 Qatar International Art Festival in Doha to exhibit various genres of Nigerian arts for enhanced global visibility, with the support of the Nigerian Embassy in Doha, the Nigerian National Gallery of Arts, the Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and others 'within the creative and diplomatic sectors' (Isenyo, 2026: 3). While this remains a positive initiative, a wider participation by other critical stakeholders in the creative and tourism industries, including the Ministry of Art, Tourism, Culture, and Creative Economy, could have enriched the experience, minimised the duplication of efforts, streamlined policy directions and ensured efficient human resource deployment. Other measures include the annual National Festival of Arts and Culture, Indigenous Games and Indigenous Cuisine, and the International Arts and Crafts Expo usually organised by the National Council for Arts and Culture (NCAC) to showcase local talents, mobilise stakeholders, uphold Nigeria's heritage and national identity, and promote cultural exchange. There is also an initiative by the Lagos State Government tagged 'Eko for Culture' that encapsulates the celebration of Lagos State's rich cultural heritage and creative endowments through cultural events, human capacity building and cultural exchange. It also celebrates the Guarantee-Trust-Bank-sponsored Lagos International Food and Drinks Festival and the Sterling-Bank-sponsored Eat Drink Festival (EDF) that feature local and international cuisine, chefs, competitions and cooking tutorials. There are similar events in other regions of the country. The Nigerian Tourism Development Authority (NTDA), in collaboration with other stakeholders creates a number of initiatives that seek to promote domestic tourism, celebrate Nigerian brands and cultural heritage, and create international awareness. These include the Tour Nigeria Campaign, Fashion Festival, and Flavours Nigeria, among others. In addition to the above, the Federal Bank of Nigeria (FBN, 2018) has a programme tagged "Creative Industry Financing Initiative" (CIFI),

which seeks to encourage existing and emerging entrepreneurs in the Nigerian creative industry with flexible and low interest loans of up to 500 million Naira, with a view to bridging the gap between the creative industries and integral and sustainable development. Beyond these localized efforts, there are various extra-national forums for collaborations and diaspora engagements that provide opportunities for cultural exchange. The Nigeria Diaspora Investment Summit, for instance, creates avenues for collaboration and partnerships by various creative entrepreneurs with governments, financiers, business owners, industry experts and other potential stakeholders, in exploring opportunities in the Nigerian setting that could include cultural products. All of these have certain practical implications and offer unique opportunities for cultural diplomacy and tourism development that require strategic and coordinated measures to bring to fruition as discussed below.

6. Practical Implications and Opportunities

A cultural diplomacy that can attract tourism flows to a destination requires some degree of deliberateness and consistency, with particular attentiveness to the bilateral dimensions of such diplomacy. Nigeria has, for instance, enjoyed strong cultural diplomatic ties with the United Kingdom stemming from a long history of colonial heritage that dates back to the 19th Century. This relationship, which has led to migration for various purposes and a large number of Nigerian diaspora in the United Kingdom, with the resulting cultural influence and people-to-people connections, is evolving into a strategic partnership between the two countries (Government of the UK, 2024). Nigeria also benefits from various degrees of cultural relations with other sovereign nations like the United States, Japan, China, India, Russia, South Korea, Malaysia, France, South Africa and others within and outside the African continent by way of academic and language exchange programmes, exhibitions, and various forms of collaborations, and leading to large populations of Nigerians abroad acting as cultural bridges. However, these relations largely appear to be lopsided and bereft of equanimity and reciprocity, as Nigeria features more as the beneficiary-recipient than a deliberate and purposeful actor. A deliberate, purposeful and well-coordinated cultural diplomacy by Nigeria with the global community, using its vibrant cultural capital and dynamic population offers it numerous opportunities for improved global

perception and tourism in-flows, which will ultimately boost its economic diversification efforts and significantly foster integral and sustainable development.

The domains of heritage promotion and preservation constitute additional avenues that Nigeria could leverage for optimized cultural diplomacy and tourism development. With multiple tangible and intangible heritage resources that depict its diverse cultures rooted in ancient civilization, pre-colonial and colonial encounters, Nigeria could reframe its cultural narrative, reshape its international reputation, and enhance its soft power. A standard starting point would be the nationalization of aspects or all of its cultural heritage assets to secure them from nationalistic idiosyncrasies and accord them priority in budgetary and policy considerations (Okure, 2020). The recent return of the stolen bronze and other artefacts from the Ancient Benin Kingdom, which has amplifies the advocacy for the repatriation of other stolen cultural resources, offers immense opportunities for attracting international visitors to the country. Nevertheless, Nigeria should push further by organising more international arts exhibitions and investing more in the promotion and conservation of its artefacts and heritage sites to induce global interest and attract tourism inflows.

Another area that offers immense opportunities for growth is that of the media and digital platforms, which have become modern tools for reaching the global audience. This would require a multi-layered approach that combines specific strategies with policy actions to drive the process. Among these would be a level of coordinated synergy between the Federal government through its Federal Ministry of Art, Culture, Tourism, and Creative Economy (FMACTCE) and that of Communication, Innovation and Digital Economy (FMCIDE) and their departments with individuals, agencies and organisations in the creative industries and the civil society at large to develop an integrated digital cultural diplomatic strategy. Secondly, there must be a purposeful community engagement strategy that leverages social media and digital platforms to create virtual museum tours and streaming services for digital storytelling, dialogues, workshops, documentaries and diaspora engagement to bring the rich cultural capital of Nigeria, including Nollywood, music, festivals and the arts among others, to the global audience.

7. Confronting Persistent Challenges

The challenges that confront cultural diplomacy practice and cultural tourism development in Nigeria are quite complex owing to its political history and the socio-economic landscape. The long years of military dictatorship, ethnic hostilities, inequalities and religious conflict, among others, seem to have, over time, created and sustained sentiments of insincerity, unaccountability and impunity that often corrode genuine leadership structures, distort national priority setting, and impede authentic political will in pursuing public interest. These challenges, which can be surmounted, manifest in a number of ways as follows.

7.1 Policy Gaps: There are gaps between existent policies and their implementation, in addition to the absence of well-defined and coherent long term policies for the execution of cultural diplomacy and cultural tourism development. Enormous resources are often expended on the formulation, reviews and revision of extant policies with little corresponding strategic measures for their implementation, monitoring and success evaluation. Also, whereas successive governments have initiated frameworks for the funding of the creative and cultural industries either directly or through ministries and agencies, such initiatives often seem incoherent, receiving varying degrees of attention across successive regimes. This regime-based approach to national policy implementation has hindered the actualization of Nigeria's cultural diplomacy and cultural tourism potential.

7.2 Infrastructural Gaps: Another vital setback to the integral and sustained development of Nigeria's cultural resources derives from inadequate and poorly framed physical, human, and organizational infrastructure that not only fall beneath global standards, but also fail to maintain the vibrancy of the industry and attract tourists and investors' interest. The transportation network, especially across roads and waterways, is underdeveloped and ill-maintained, the ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) responsible for the promotion of cultural resources tend to absorb and retain a large work force that is poorly trained and ill-equipped, while their organizational structure lack the mechanisms for monitoring efficiency and measuring results. The Nigerian Tourism Development Masterplan (2010: 3) had, in this respect, proposed measures for "a clear, identifiable positioning of Nigeria as

cultural and regional conference destination in the tourism market place...that is attractive to visitors that are sensitive to the cultural and social mores.” These would include creating tourism development clusters with specialised product qualities and market appeal, and overall infrastructural and human resource development. These have been largely ignored.

7.3 Budgeting and Funding: Cultural diplomacy and cultural tourism development require deliberate and strategic budgeting and sustained funding to create suitable atmosphere for investment and partnerships between governments and other actors in the private sector. The Nigerian government, knowing that its tourism strength derives more from cultural and heritage assets requires deliberate and sustained funding mechanisms that are governed by transparency and accountability to empower the cultural and creative industries in developing authentic quality products for local, regional and international consumption. Additionally, strategic funding for the development and promotion of non-cultural tourism resources in the Niger Delta riverine and coastal regions like beaches, water sports and fishing, sea cruising and other aqua tourism products would go a long way in boosting the nation’s tourism infrastructure and appeal, as well as improve its overall image.

7.4 Security: One of the most visible and widely acknowledged threats to Nigeria’s cultural progress and tourism development is insecurity. There is a general and persistent landscape of insecurity that not only mars the regular celebration of the nation’s rich and diverse cultures, but also deters local and international tourists from exploring these cultural frontiers. Heightened rates of kidnapping for ransom, banditry, terrorist incursions and other acts of violence on the one hand, and the seeming complicity of the security operatives and their inability to successfully confront these challenges have combined to weaken cultural institutions, generate apathy for travelling and discourage investment in cultural resources.

7.5 Destination Image Management and Branding: Destination and image management and branding has long been identified a vital “missing link” in Nigeria’s tourism development (Okure, 2021: 70) and international perception. Modern social media seems replete with misinformation about the Nigerian state and its leadership infrastructure, which have combined with other forces to generate a negative global

image bordering on corruption, impunity, insecurity and economic instability, among others. The nation requires robust investment in destination image management and branding in collaboration with destination management organisations (DMOs), cultural agencies and local communities. The Nigerian Tourism Development Authority (NTDA), which has a clear mandate in this respect, could partner with the National Council for Arts and Culture (NCAC) and other tourism agencies like the National Institute for Hospitality and Tourism (NIHOTOUR); Hospitality and Tourism Management Association of Nigeria (HATMAN); Federation of Tourism Association of Nigeria (FTAN); National Association of Nigeria Travel Agencies (NANTA); and the National Commission for Museums and Monuments (NCMM) to foster the destination management and image branding of Nigeria through integrated planning, development and packaging, promotion, marketing and distribution of tangible and intangible cultural products, especially through the social media and other information and communication technological (ICT) infrastructure. Moreover, there could be an integrated branding strategy that unifies the creative and cultural heritage industries – cuisine, music, films, fashion, festivals, literature, and crafts – in a targeted tourism campaign.

7.6 Inter-ministerial Synergy: Mobilising cultural diplomacy for the development of cultural tourism requires purposeful and sustained synergy between federal ministries, especially the Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs (FMFA), the Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation (FMINO) and the Federal Ministry of Art, Culture, Tourism, and Creative Economy (FMACCE) as key institutions for leveraging Nigeria’s cultural assets and creative industries for national and international consumption. Such synergy should aim, among other, at broadening the collaboration network and strategic partnerships with local communities, creative entrepreneurs, airlines and hotels operators for packaging the nation’s cultural resources, including festivals and events as tourism products. This inter-ministerial synergy could also lead to frameworks for the training of cultural attachés and tourism professionals in global best practices, and forge regional collaboration with other members of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) for promoting regional tourism routes, with Nigeria as the leading actor.

7.7 Local Community Involvement: Local community involvement has often been overlooked in the formulation and implementation of cultural policies and tourism development strategies. Yet, local communities and their leaders are the rightful custodians of the peoples' culture, and whose knowledge and inputs should not be ignored. Cultural authenticity requires that cultural resources be traced to their true origins. A UNESCO-recognised inventory of Nigeria's cultural resources (UNESCO, n.d.) for instance, reveals numerous individuals, groups and communities with unique oral traditions, languages, performing arts, social practices, rituals and social events, knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe, and traditional craftsmanship that truly capture the essence of its rich cultural heritage that could be leveraged to strengthen national identity, foster unity and empower communities through cultural entrepreneurship. This, if well utilized, would also provide channels for creating a formidable cultural diplomatic frontier and attracting international cultural tourism flows into the country.

8. Conclusion

Nigeria has a strong, versatile and dynamic cultural portfolio that offers enormous opportunities for global influence through impactful cultural diplomacy and a tourism-led economic diversification and development. What is required is a reliable and well-defined framework for the implementation of cultural diplomacy and an unsullied political will for executing such framework. To counter the current global negative image that borders on insecurity, religious intolerance and corruption, vigorous efforts and suitable strategies must be deployed, first, to promote, manage, protect and invest in its vast cultural resources, and then project itself through them to the world as a wholesome, authentic, innovative, eco-friendly, technology driven and humane country through cultural diplomacy to attract international positive global attention. Nigeria has to discard of a workforce of mere political appointees and engage learned, well-informed and dedicated patriots, while also de-emphasising international conference attendance to focus more on genuine policy implementation that engages cultural entrepreneurs and artists whose works create jobs and opportunities. When cultural diplomacy promotes culture, it also creates desires for cultural experience that in turn boosts tourism incentives.

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